

Curvature Deflections – 8T

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Abstract:

Following the previous papers about the gravity mediated by light and Einstein theory flaws due to referring to fermions cluster rather than bosonic fields as the cause for the curvature effect. One will argue for possible chronology of events in which fermion cluster could affect the notion of gravity. Those clusters by emitting another set of curvature elements can deflect an original set curvature that is linearly polarized toward a less linear state of polarization.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 \dots \quad (1.12)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.13)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.14)$$

Suppose a fermion cluster got scattered and emitted as a result an additional set of curvature, i.e. photons or any additional prime amount given by the primorial coupling constants series. In addition, suppose the additional curvature cluster now directing or moving toward the path of the original bosonic cluster given by (1.14).

$$\mathfrak{m}: \sum_{j=1}^K \delta g_j \rightarrow \sum_{j=1}^K \delta g_j > 0 \quad (1.15)$$

Equation () describe bosonic curvatures propagate from matter clusters, which we require by the 8T:

$$\sum_{j=1}^K \delta g_j = 0 \quad (1.16)$$

Now suppose that linearly polarized curvature given by (1.14) and the deflecting set of curvature given by equation (1.15):

$$\sum_{j=1}^K \delta g_j + \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \neq \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i \quad (1.17)$$

Linearly polarized now become an inner product, curvature mixture on the manifold. So the bottom line is that despite matter clusters do not affect the curvature distribution on the metric, they can create deflections on linearly polarized light and by doing so causing it to have less linearity by creating a new inner product of those two sets. In other words, their effect is indirect.

References

- [2] O. Manor. "8 Theory – Proving Einstein Wrong about Gravity" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "Modifying the Rules of Gravity" In: (2021)